

TECHNOLOGY FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF MEDIKOMPETENCE OF STUDENTS

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Abstract. *The article will determine theorian and methodological aspects of the mediacompetival, philosophical, pedagogical and psychological, technical and methodological, technical and methodological, technical capabilities in the students, and the strategic requirements of the media of the media, to improve the media environmental capabilities, the gradual development of mediacompetentity - adjustment of technologies for the implementation of the technologies of the markets, the content of students, the demands of students, the design of creative sessions, the audience is designed to develop the audience, and the development of the audience, designing nonverbal, and the development of creative, creative thinking.*

Keywords: *medicompetyivity, engineer, specialty, psychological and pedagogical literature, methods, research methods, Assembly, problematicization, didactic opportunities.*

Introduction. The technologies of future specialists in global specialists have been widely used in the educational process. Platforms for development of professional competencies of future specialists throughout the media and information are created and the possibility of open and remote professional education (CONTINUING professional development - CD) on these platforms. During the development of digital technologies and the intensification of educational platforms, special attention is paid to the implementation of medical competencies mechanisms in them. By recent years, developing the professionalism of the world in the world, and the assessment of professionalism of the teacher of the future vocabalical education; Research related to the development of the capacity are being carried out.

But during this period, nothing is blinded blindly, each source is carefully studied and the content is being created creatively based on the current conditions of medita. The expansion of the global fields, including through modern mediatings, have the opportunity to improve the level of mediacomompentent, independent education and independent development in experts.

Higher education institutions cannot be prepared by unlimited training of unlimited specialists. This fact created conditions for the implementation of a large number of diversity in recent years, where the development of mediaCompomentism have been studied from students to military and engineers. During this period, the subject of the media common of the specialists of the society's specialists and the competence of the competence of the forensic training also became the subject of the study.

For example, the problem of development of mediaCompeterancy in higher education institutions N.Yu.Kyzova [17], E.A.Stolbnikova [16]. Development of information competence of the mediaompetientation A.V.bererin [3], L.P.GRishchenko [4], A.SK.Karkechenko [9], P.N.Kuzya [10], V.Yu.Nikishina [12], O.M.Chuban [18], L.B.Shtein, studied in the work of others.

In the process of studying the research, it was found that the research on the development of mediaCompetentions directly in future vocational education teachers. The analysis confirms that the problem we choose is little, and the mediaCompetern of future vocational education teachers should be addressed. Among the most important ones, it is necessary to record the following. In the preparation of future teaching training teachers:• атамашунослик асоси тартибга солинмаган;

- The content and specific features of mediaCompentership are not identified;
- A pedagogical model that allows medicalpetidity to develop;
- The principles of this model development are not identified;
- Stages of medical development, methods and means of technologies have not been identified;
- Pedagogical conditions for the effective development of mediaCompentity are not defined.

State educational standards, qualification programs, curricula define the importance of developing mediaompomethnetic in higher education institutions and teachers of vocational education. This includes this task as a key. Today, this term is widely used, the term "media" is inextricably linked with terms such as "media", "mass communications". In the new dictionary in English, "media" [English massmedia - the media] has meaning as massmedia. In the same dictionary, the second meaning of the term is the first part of the term, saying that the media belongs to the media, for example: mediaolding, media companies, media regrams, mediation, mediaforum".

Dictionary for vocational technologies "suggests the point of view of Mediapedagog A.V.afedorov [14], it (media, massmedia) - (public communication means - reproduction, recording, copying, ad Means of exchange between the subject (medianamant's author) and object (mass audience). This definition clearly emphasizes the tradition of "media" and the media into each other, which will begin to unite two functions: Technological and communicators.

O.A.Koysinov [11] expresses the opinion that the quality of vocational education in his research work can be ensured precisely by the formation of the competence of the future teacher and the development of professional pedagogical creativity, and believes that the development of technologies for the implementation of the educational process is one of the most important tasks of modernization of vocational education.

K.Karimov [8] noted that the self-education and self-development ability of the educators will increase in the process of Professional Development established in the information and Communication Technology Environment.

F.Gaffarov [5] in his research work, an electronic system of assessing the knowledge and skills of students in special subjects has been created, and a software has been developed that allows the interaction and exchange of experience among special science teachers of the regional vocational colleges.

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M.Vahobov In his article titled "Introduction of state educational standards based on the kompetential approach to practice – an important factor in the development of mediacompetence of students", vakhobov noted that "in the present century, the exchange of information is one of the

most important tasks of the educational system by means of the development of mediacompetence, mediacompetence and mediacompetence in the youth, in the

H.Kadyrov believes that the mediacompetency of the teacher is a competence of professional skills, which is connected with information and communication technologies, which are necessary for education in the information environment, provide effective activities of the teacher, critical thinking, acceptance, mastering, creative processing, transmission, storage, quality education and distribution. Through the computer-based tool, there are the main features and advantages of instructional technology, which are as follows [24]:

- develop independent thinking and creative abilities in the direction of learning;
- in the educational process, the teacher participates as a consultant;
- provides an active link between the means and resources of Information Technology;
- it is ensured that the learning process is comfortable and productive;
- independent work and independent research skills are formed.

Materials and methods. The sharp increase in the information environment requires the need for theoretical knowledge and practical skills in the formation of competence in the use of information and communication technologies from specialists working in various fields. But in the process of professional development, however, it is limited to providing ready-made recommendations to teachers on the use of information and communication technology tools and ignoring the professional growth of the teacher. In order to introduce ICT into the educational process, of course, it is necessary that professional qualities are formed at a high level in pedagogy. Therefore, in the process of professional development, attention should be paid to the development of personal and professional qualities in the audience.

It is also necessary to develop methods for the formation of practical skills in secondary schools by providing theoretical knowledge on the use of various electronic programs in the educational process.

The main goals of the use of information and Communication Technology in the course of the lesson (to increase computer literacy in the student, to obtain information from non-standard sources, to master the independent knowledge of the student, to develop thinking skills and creative research on the basis of the application of information and Communication Technology in teaching) are presented in Figure

Teaching of subjects in educational institutions is carried out with the help of educational laboratory equipment, computer and various means (multimedia, computer lingophone, electronic educational programs, electronic textbooks, electronic whiteboard, television, video glozok, etc.). In particular, the organization of ICT-based classes in educational institutions is mainly used in four directions:

- as an object of study;
- in the management of Education;
- as a technical tool for teaching;
- in scientific-pedagogical research.

Formation of potential, independent and creative solution of professional problems, personal and general education professional activity is able to become aware of the training of a competitive specialist is the main tasks facing professors and teachers of the institution of Higher Education. The increase in the volume of data processed by the student means that there will be a

burden on memory, which means that mastering a very large amount of information at the same time is carried out only with the help of innovative educational techniques [23. 6898-6902].

In this regard, to achieve the effectiveness of training, it is necessary to introduce innovative educational methods and technologies of teaching. Innovation is the application of new content and new educational techniques to practice. Methods of education these are ways of interrelated activities of professors and students towards mastering the knowledge, skills and skills related to development and development in the educational process. Innovative educational methods motivate students to practice and think, the most effective innovative methods of teaching are used in order to improve the quality of specialist training, increase students' cognitive activity, generate their creative potential, organize the educational process at a high level. As the main objectives of these innovative techniques, it will provide the exchange of information necessary for the development of mediacompetence in the teachers of the future professional education, to identify the process and trends of the development of mediacompetence, to identify the existing difficulties and to find ways to overcome them, to use the information-analytical function that classifies the successful, with the help of mediavocites, which create conditions for the development of important professional aspects, it was aimed to faollashtir personal qualities that introduce successful adaptation in medimuhit, apply them to professional activities through the creation of situations, and serve to work with media reports and to search for the necessary information [22].

On the basis of the methodological support of the blocks of the program for the development of mediacompetence of future teachers of vocational education (Table 1) was used in the teaching of the subject "educational technology". This method was applied to the educational process on the basis of the stages of development of mediacompetence in support of supply.

Table 1

The content of the science of educational technology the technologies, tools and stages of development of mediacompetence

№	Subject of training	Technologies for the development of mediacompetence	Tools
	Subject, purpose and objectives of the science "educational technology". The science of "educational technologies" as an independent field of pedagogy	Theoretical, Experience-productive, Creative	Mass media
	Features of the educational process in Professional educational institutions.	Theoretical	Mass media
	Interactive strategies of education in Professional educational institutions and problematic education.	Experience-productive	Media resources of Education. Analysis of Media texts
	Educational technology in accelerating the activity of students.	Creative	Voice training tools
	Science and personality-oriented technology of Education.	Theoretical	Media resources of Education. Analysis of Media texts

	Technology in the organization and effective management of the educational process.	Experience-produktov	Mediamohite
	Educational tools – as a structural element of educational technology.	Creative	Media resources of Education. Analysis of Media texts
	Educational technology that develops critical thinking.	Experience-produktov	Media resources of Education. Analysis of Media texts
	Qualification requirements for a professional education teacher.	Theoretical	Media resources of Education. Analysis of Media texts
	Technological development of educational process. Pedagogical technologies – as educational technologies.	Creative	Visual education tools
	Theory and features of the innovative activity of the teacher of Professional educational institutions. Activities and pedagogical skills of the teacher.	Theoretical	Visual education tools
	Scientific basis of Organization of pedagogical labor.	Theoretical	Audiovisual media Education
	Design of the application of educational technology in the teaching of special subjects educational technology	Experience-productive, creative	Stage and scenario
	Keys stadi training technology	Experience-productive, creative	Stage and scenario
	Modular methods of teaching professional subjects	Theoretical	Media stereotypes
	Technology of development of Test assignments		Mediamohite
	Graphic organizers technique	Creative	Media stereotypes
	Computer education technology	Experience-productive, creative	Mediamohite

Let's look at the methodology of passing the lesson in the framework of one subject from the subject "educational technology". That is, the topic "scientific theoretical basis of the science of educational technology".

Basic concepts: educational technology, stages of development, pedagogical technology, developed countries, Technology, Technology Centers, technology essence, levels of pedagogical technology.

Classification of educational technology. Axiomatic approach to educational technology, problematic and modular teaching, personality-oriented educational technology, technology of accelerating education on the basis of marking models of educational material, taxonomy of educational objectives.

Innovation process structural structures and legislation. An axiological approach to innovation activities.

Akmeology. Factors of achieving high professionalism. Creative individuality. The concept of the term creativeness refers to.

Skills that characterize creativity. Stages of creativeness in teacher activity. A reflexive approach to teacher innovation activities. Conditions for the formation of the innovation activity of the teacher. The educational and cognitive activities of students in the organization of teacher innovation activities and the importance of its management [22].

Applied educational technologies: intelligent attack, working in small groups, Cluster, techniques of advertising preparation using media educational tools.

Training

- Questions will be asked that will enable knowledge of the subject.
- Divide students into 4 subgroups by optional character.
- Each group analyzes the stages of formation of individual "educational technologies".
- * Organizes the work of advertising preparation on the content, purpose, functions and necessity of educational technology and introduces students to the norms of evaluation.

Faollashtiruvchi questions:

1. What is the content of the course?
2. What tasks should you perform during the course?
3. What knowledge can you master during the course?

1-assignment. Write and comment on the stages of the formation of pedagogical technologies in accordance with the order numbers?

2-task: preparation of advertising on the topic in small groups.

Terms of advertising:

1. Each group must develop its own name, slogan, emblem.
2. Advertising is required to write information material.
3. In the information material, the content and essence of pedagogical technologies are required to be illuminated.
4. Must organize the presentation of advertising.

Table 2

Norms of advertising evaluation

№	Score for the slogan and emblem (Up to 10 points)	Information material understandable and attractive (up to 10 points)	For the skill of revealing the essence of pedagogical technologies (Up to 10 points)
1.			
2.			

3-Assignment. Find the correct answer.

a) Educational technology it [23]:

b) an orderly collection of the most accessible means of communication, information and management and the means of teaching (process-descriptive aspect of teaching technology), which provides a means of ensuring a guaranteed achievement of the educational goal and the results achieved in the current conditions and at the set time;

c) an orderly sum of the most accessible path and means of teaching of information and management, which provides a means of ensuring the guaranteed achievement of the educational goal and the results achieved under the existing conditions and at the set time (process-descriptive aspect of educational technology);

d) an orderly collection of means of communication, teaching, which provides a means of guaranteeing the achievement of the educational goal and the results achieved in the existing conditions and at the set time (process-descriptive aspect of teaching technology);

III. Rezultaty. It is an important aspect to see the accuracy of the theoretical situation developed as part of the framework necessary for any scientific pedagogical research by experimentation. D.F. We agree with Ilyasov's views that the pedagogical experiment allows "to reveal the results of monitoring, the essence of processes and phenomena in the cycle of determining the planned conditions" [7]. Proceeding from these points of view, we understand that constant monitoring of changes in the educational process, which is carried out in the influence of the analyzed aspects, is necessary and necessary. In our study, these aspects of effective implementation of the set of pedagogical conditions were developed and theoretically based on the model of development of mediacompetence in future teachers of vocational education.

Most researchers in their research work have identified criteria as a sign that allows them to assess the quality of a process or object. As the main criterion in our work, the regular action of the teachers of the future vocational education at the level of new and relatively advanced mediacompetence was used. We distinguish the main four levels: inadequate; situational; professional-adequate; creative. In Table 3, we bring their description.

Table 3

Description of the level of development of future vocational education teachers mediacompetence

Not enough level	Future professional education teachers use the methods they have learned before in the implementation of mediafood, work only on the basis of a sample, it will not be possible to perform creative work. They try not to participate in mediamulocots, they are well aware of mediavocytetes and their methods of use, they pull themselves out of showing activity in mediamuhit. Mediamuhit lacks knowledge, skills and skills to operate independently. Mediaphylaxis and mediacompetence do not understand the essence; for subordinates, employees and other students, mediamuhit cannot competently formulate the tasks that must be solved using it. In them, personal qualities inherent in future professional education teachers of mediacompetence are not sufficiently formed.
Situational degree	Future professional education teachers will understand the content and essence of mediacompetence, the importance of mediamuloqot in interaction with other representatives of mediamuhit. In them, some skills related to work in mediamuhit were formed, but no skills were formed. Mediamuhit sometimes steers creative assignments, but lack of in-depth knowledge and skill formability does not give them the opportunity to make extensive and active use of their fantasies. Mediafault employees and co-school students under the arm cannot regularly weigh in on game situations, show mistrust in making decisions related to mediafield management, and in most cases make wrong or most ineffective decisions.
Profession-enough level	The degree of development of mediacompatibility in the student is characterized by consciousness, criticism, compactness, efficiency, independence, he is able to freely use the skills available in mediamuhit in his activities. Students demonstrate self-development, interest and needs in the process of shading mediacompetence. Within the framework of their professional activities, the students will be able to use the standard principles of mediafety, as well as adapt to the rules and norms of effective professional communication in mediamuhit. Students will confidently apply their knowledge, skills and skills in the mediacompetent field, but will not be able to implement a creative approach when making relatively effective educational decisions.
Creative level	Teachers of future vocational education realize the content, essence and importance of mediacompetence, actively use optimal mediavocytetes, show high creative activity, be able to work independently and effectively in mediamuhit. They actively use the information and communication components of the media in the educational process. Future professional education teachers effectively cooperate with all participants of the mediamuhit communication process, properly evaluate the information received in mediamuhit, find them, learn critically and make creative processing possible. They will have the necessary professional personal qualities and skills to apply them in educational mediamuhit. In these aspects, the staff should be able to make the mediatoptics clear, error-free and fast, in addition to their mobilization and active faith

Since mediacompetence manifests itself as a complex phenomenon, it is necessary to distinguish all its indicators in order to fully interpret it. In the development and implementation of the kompetent approach, we determined that future vocational training teachers mediacompetence will be composed of important professional knowledge, skills and skills related to the implementation of an effective educational process based on the involvement of mediamuhit.

We consider the positive changes recorded in the manifestation of the listed indicators as a result of the implementation of the model of development of mediacompetence in the future teachers of vocational education. This, in turn, suggests the correctness of the pedagogical conditions, the expediency of our developed theoretical conclusions.

Any indicators offered can be represented at different levels. In the process of our experience-test, which we have developed, we determine the characteristics of their level of equal expression.

Characteristic features of these qualities: orientation to highly productive professional activity, independence and self-control, abandonment of standard template actions, difficult promotion of new ideas.

Description of the degree of development of the proposed personal qualities expressed in Table 4

Table 4

The scale level criteria for determining the extent to which significant professional personal qualities are developed within mediacompetence in future vocational education teachers

Low	The clarification of the low degree of paralysis of personal qualities in rare cases in the process of mediafaalism presents a certain difficulty in collecting and placing information in mediamuhit labor activity. It also leads to a lack of interest in the effective implementation of goal-oriented mediafaularity.
Middle	This stage is expressed in the systematic use of the components of medifaularity in the provision of partially effective activities in mediamuhit from certain information and communication aspects. This situation is reflected in the performance of certain mediavasifas in the effective cooperation of mediacompetent employees.
High	Mastery of the level of formation of important professional personal qualities, which are expressed in the complex and creative acquisition of all components of mediacompetence, skillful selection of topical mediavocytas, collection, storage, processing and critical analysis of the necessary information for mediamuhit, as well as competent mastering of their own private mediahabars, leads to effective management of the institution using mediavocytas.

The experimental and test works were carried out during the 2019-2022 academic years and 457 respondents were involved in 1 - 4 courses. The main experimental and testing works of the research were carried out in three stages at the National Research University "Tashkent Institute of irrigation and agricultural engineers:

1. In the process of training Bachelor-teachers in the direction of vocational education in the stage of substantive experience, pedagogical activity was organized aimed at developing their mediacompetence, determining the level of development of mediacompetentities in them.

2. At the stage of developing experience, practical and methodological activity was organized on the basis of the recommended instructions, instructions, methodological developments, casings and forms of execution of problematic situational tasks in pedagogical and technological activity.

3. In order to develop the mediacompetence of future teachers of vocational education in the experimental stage, it was analyzed the development of mediacompetence on the basis of problematic situational assignments encountered in pedagogical and technological activities, carrying out creative exercises, problematic videographs encountered in pedagogical and

technological activities, and the effectiveness of the methodology used, as well as the level of development of mediacompetents in.

A total of 457 students from the experimental and control groups were involved in order to get answers to the questionnaire and questionnaire questions under the conditions of the study.

Based on the questions that require knowledge about mediacompetence in the case of this questionnaire, the results were analyzed, summarized at the beginning of the experiment and at the end of the experiment were obtained on the answers to the questions on the knowledge of the level of mediacompetence provided for in the questionnaire and its application in the professional field, and it

Table 5

There is mediacompetence, and the indicators that are positively reflected in the questions posed by them

№	Content of questions	Experience Group 242 control group 215			
		Experiment		Experiment	
1	What is Media?	56%	54%	82%	58%
2	What resources do you use when preparing for training, divide by the percentage	51%	53%	72%	57%
3	Have you ever tried to create your own site, Internet page, videroligini, presentation?	50%	49%	78%	51%
4	Do you participate in Internet discussions? How?	58%	60%	83%	62%
5	Do you know what Skype is?	40%	43%	79%	55%
6	What information are you looking for in the media?	66%	67%	88%	70%
7	You have a professional task in front of you, but you do not lack the information to solve it. Where Are you looking for?	65%	53%	85%	55%
8	You have been instructed to present a professional problem beautifully. What do you use for this?	58%	61%	79%	62%
9	How would you like to have computer programs?	56%	55%	81%	61%

Based on the data obtained from the experimental-test work, we can conclude that the experimental-test work that we have organized is reliable, the effect of the identified conditions

on the development of mediacompetence in future teachers of vocational education is significant [23,25].

III. Discussion. Educators are obliged to have a general idea of the media, and there is a classification of media that, on a number of grounds, divides them into several groups: according to the types of basic media (press, radio, Film, Television, video, Computer Networks, etc.); according to the channels of reception (audio, video, audiovisual, labeled, text, pictorial); according to the place of use (individual, collective, mass, at home, ; in the direction of socialization (ideological, political, moral-educational, reading-cognitive, aesthetic, environmental, economic); according to the goals and objectives of Use (acquisition of information, education, communication, problem-solving, leisure, social); according to the results of exposure to a person (expansion of worldview, self-awareness and upbringing, independent education, regulation of the state of socialization, self-management) [181, 130]. It is worth noting that getting acquainted with the classification of the media, in our opinion, teachers will clarify how the media activities will be carried out, what channels they will be put into operation, what types they will manifest themselves in, the use of the necessary component of the synthetic model block to the Kabas.

The next stage of the theoretical block will be the acquaintance of educators with the theoretical foundations of mediat education. In the pedagogical Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan, media education is a special branch of pedagogy and is considered by students as a social direction that studies the laws of mass communication. The main task of the mediat education is to prepare the new generation for the conditions of the modern information environment, to receive various information, to teach a person to understand them, to know its influence on the human psyche, to master the methods of communication on the basis of nonverbal forms of communication, modern information technology and technical means, in other words, to prepare The actual problems of mediapedagogy are a number of Russian A.V.Sharikov[20], A.V.It was studied in the studies of Fedorov[14] and other scientists. The ultimate goal of mediat education is to develop the mediacompetence of the students, to realize the position of the media in life, to enable them to carry out their communication with the media.

At all stages of its development, the media education was closely related to the media as a set of material and social values in the media sector, as well as the historically defined system of their development and functioning in the society. This term is understood in two different ways. On the one hand, the issue goes about the socio-cultural events related to the media (the world of television, the world of gazeta and magazines, the world of radio, Internet resources, etc.). On the other hand, they see it as the interaction of man with the world of media, his creative manifestation of self through the means of communication, ensuring a full inclusion of man in society at the General end. It should be said that the discussion of the leading models-their conceptual foundations, areas of application, forms and techniques used in the activities of the mediatre-is of great interest to practitioners-educators who are preparing to apply their mediatre experiences in working with students and students.

Also, the interest of the teachers in the problem of Genesis in our country's mediatre education, the formation of apparatus in its concepts is coming to its fore. Based on the study of the history of the stages of the development of media education in Uzbekistan [Fedorov[14], Chelysheva] it can be said that the concepts of media education cover specific evolyusiyu, the creation of technical means, records, copying, reproduction, storage, distribution, reception of information in mass audiences and among authors, exchange of information, etc.

The current state-of-the-art media education system has several main directions:

1) in the world of the Internet and video, cinema, television, radio, the press, the future profession of the media education — journalists, editors, directors, producers, actors, operators, etc.;

2) the process of professional development of professors and teachers of the higher educational institution and school students on mediamadanity, the future pedagogues of the Pedagogical Institute and universities;

3) integration of the medium of education as part of the general education of students and students, ordinary school students, students of higher educational institutions of secondary special educational institutions, respectively, with traditional educational sciences, as well as independent (special, elective, circular) subjects;

4) extra-curricular institutions and recreation centers (houses of culture ,work of extracurricular centers, aesthetic and artistic education, various clubs);

5) press-assisted school students, students and adult distance media education, such as television, radio, video, DVD, Internet system (the big role here is played by media criticism);

6) independent (continuous) media education, which is carried out throughout the whole life of a person [Fedorov, 2004].

In the next decades, the world, including in the practice of media education, is increasingly focusing on the problem of mediacompetence (mediacompetence).

Competence is a " characteristic that is given to a person by assessing the effectiveness and effectiveness of his efforts aimed at studying a certain range of tasks and problems that are relevant to this community in an expanded way " [Ivanov[6]]. This concept is in the context of education "mainly the result of the important and leading abilities possessed by the individual himself. That's what they "help people achieve their personal goals that are important to them..."[Raven, 2002[13]].

Today, the modern organization of the educational process allows the growing younger generation to live in this world worthy of being a full-fledged citizen of their country, possessing academic knowledge, skills and qualifications. It is no secret to anyone that now a modern person lives in an information environment, "his new life environment, the reality of modern culture, the media, the penetration of new technologies into all spheres of human existence" [Kirillova, 9]. Media (mass media) has become not only a mechanism of data transmission, but also the main means of production of modern culture. The information revolution, which has become an integral part of our lives, has led Uzbekistan to enter the world global information environment, an important component of modern civilization.

Identification and development of the motivational sphere in the process of media education is one of the urgent tasks of today's mediapedagogy. The task of the educator is not only to understand the student's choice of a particular medium, but also to expand their emotional or gedonistic, intellektual, creative, ethical and other communication motivations with the media. For this purpose, the educator will have to create an atmosphere of mutual trust in the dialogue of cooperation with students.

IV.Conclucions. Therefore, in order to effectively organize work with materials of the works of the mediamadanity, it is necessary that the modern teacher has well mastered the basic methods, means and methods of analysis of various genres, forms and types. Therefore, in the educational process, many things are determined by the teacher's existing personal attitude towards mediamadanism, the techniques he uses in the educational process. The creation of a solid creative

(collaborative creativity), dialogue environment, based on the free expression of one's own thoughts — all such factors have their positive impact on the activities of the mediator.

Development of creative and practical-active indicators of pedagogical mediacompetence. The process of educators' preparation for the implementation of the mediatic foil is very vivid: it implies the effective and active application of creative and didactic game assignments on the basis of the study of theoretical materials, the study of works of mediaticism in practical training. As a result of the performance of creative tasks, educators will have the opportunity to apply their knowledge from media club, cinema, circle, faculties of various age categories to the practice of a higher educational institution. The practical and active indicators of mediacompetence constitute "the practical skills of independent selection for the creation and dissemination of Mediamatns (including — personally and created by a team of authors) of various genres and genres, active independent reading skills in the media sphere" [14].

Creative indicators itself are associated with the media "quot; the level of creative initiation (perceptive, playful, artistic, research, etc.), brightly expressed in various forms of activity.), will show [15].

In the course of the course of the training of the mediator, an extremely important component in the practical training of teachers, which they conduct with their students, is the introduction of the acquired knowledge, skills and skills into practice.

An important aspect in working with teachers is focusing on the study of the techniques of media education which are seen as the teacher and student work method which is considered as the most basic aid in achieving the objectives of media education [14]. The development of knowledge and methods of activity based on the study of the works of the Bundamediamadaniyyat takes place at the following levels:

- * apply knowledge and methods of activity in media material;
- take consciously and keep in mind;
- * creative application of knowledge on media and media management.

The classification of media education techniques can be presented as follows:

- on the sources of acquired knowledge: oral (lecture, conversation, explanation, discussion); visual (illustration and demonstration of mediamatns); practical (organization of various practical sessions on media materials);

- on the level of cognitive activity: illustrative-explanatory (media is the expression of a certain message by the teacher, the assimilation of this material by the audience); reproductive (teaching students the methods of performing such exercises and Assignments through the development and application of various assignments, exercises on the basis of media materials by the educator), problematic (problematic analysis of a certain identified mediamatn or organization of activities) [15]. Among the most common methods of Russian mediapedagogy are oral, visual, reproductive, research, euristic, problematic, didactic game techniques.

In the process of media education, various pedagogical methods are used. Methods of teaching — "concrete cooperation operations carried out in the educational process and between the student and the teacher. Teaching methods are defined based on the content of the subject, the cognitive activity carried out and the purpose of application. Methods of conformity of methods at the level of educational science constitute even holistic methodological systems" [glossary of terms pertaining to pedagogy, 2003, b. 216].

Pedagogical methods are determined by common didactic methods, and each specific methodology or pedagogical technology can combine many pedagogical methods in its own way,

the choice of which is determined based on the characteristics of the educational content. In this, the main attention will be paid to the level of planning of the training material being mastered, the methods, the available tools for their implementation, the level of effectiveness of this or that method being used.

The determination of the critical moment that determines the choice of a particular pedagogical technology in the medium is determined depending on the material that the educator chooses in the medium of Education (printing, Audiovisual media, computer technology, etc.). Taking into account the integration of different media materials, in the process of mediated education, in most cases, complex methods are used, which take into account the peculiarities of different mediums. Method of Education- "expression of concrete methods and tools of technical pedagogical activity in some educational processes". The methodology used in the process of media education is considered to be the process of teaching on the basis of the requirements of the educational process, teaching, dialogic form of teaching, improvisation, variability of pedagogical and student activity, as well as the principles of the media activity in this plan of the content of Education [14].

Creative assignments in media materials perform educational, adaptation, developmental functions:

- educational function is directed to the acquisition of knowledge on the analysis of media, the theory of their understanding and the law;
- adaptation function- this refers to the skills of applying knowledge in different unfamiliar conditions;
- developmental-motivational (compensatory, therapeutic, recreative, etc.), willpower and other personal characteristics and attributes, creative communication experiences with the media.

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